

Metal contamination in cultivated vegetables and soil receiving untreated industrial wastewater

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Abstract : The present study focuses on the analysis of industrial wastewater, characterization of agricultural soil and to examine the heavy metal (Pb, Cd, Mn, Zn and Cu) content in some selected vegetables grown on agricultural land receiving untreated wastewater. The unscientific disposal of untreated wastewater has resulted in an accumulation of heavy metals in soils which may not only result in soil contamination, but also lead to elevated metal uptake by vegetables/crops and ultimately affect the food chain. The concentrations (mg/L) of heavy metals in the wastewater samples ranged between Pb : 0.082–0.279, Cd : 0.007–0.098, Mn : 0.697–0.875, Zn : 0.595–0.887 and Cu : 0.362–0.482. Average metal concentration in untreated wastewater was in the sequence of Mn > Zn > Cu > Pb > Cd, wastewater irrigated contaminated soil also followed the same sequence though BCF followed the sequence of Cd > Mn > Zn > Pb > Cu. The high concentration of Cd was found in *Phaseolus vulgaris* (9.865 mg/kg) with its bioconcentration factor (BCF) value (3.446) followed by *Pisum sativum* (Ave. : 9.742 mg/kg; BCF : 3.403) and *Spinacia oleracea* (Ave. : 9.241 mg/kg; BCF: 3.228). High level of metal concentrations was also observed in the other vegetables analyzed. This may be due to the accumulation of heavy metals in the agricultural soil due to long-term irrigation. The higher values of metal concentration and BCF indicated heavy metal contamination in the wastewater irrigated site that is may creates a major threat of negative impact on human health.

Keywords : Wastewater irrigation, heavy metal contamination, vegetables, BCF, health risk.

Introduction

Application of industrial wastewater to agricultural land has become more popular in recent years as an alternative means of treatment and disposal which are useful sources of plant nutrients; and such wastewater may often contain high amounts of various organic and inorganic substances as well as toxic heavy metals. Anthropogenic sources of heavy metals in soils are associated with various industrial activities like application of industrial/urban effluents, waste disposal, atmospheric deposition, vehicular exhaust and long term application of sewage sludge in agricultural field^{1,2}. The unscientific disposal of untreated or undertreated wastewater has resulted in an accumulation of heavy metals in soils which may not only result in soil contamination, but also lead to elevated metal uptake by vegetables/crops, and ultimately

effect the food chain. Elevated metal content in soil facilitates hyper accumulation of metals in crops/vegetables through root uptake and also by leaf absorption. However, intake of metal-contaminated vegetables may pose a risk to the human health. Some vegetables are able to accumulate high levels of metals from the soil³⁻⁶ and prolonged consumption of contaminated foodstuffs can cause changes in natural ecosystems and consequently result in human fatal diseases through the food chain⁷⁻¹⁴.

Contamination of agricultural soil by the wastewater irrigation had become a serious environmental problem because it poses a serious threat to human health. Various soil quality parameters like pH, organic matter, cation exchange capacity etc. are known to affect the availability of heavy metals for uptake by plants¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Heavy metals are extremely persis-

tent in nature; are absorbed through the plant roots and subsequently mobilized to above ground vegetative parts. Metal accumulation in different vegetative parts depends upon various factors like chemical form of metals, their translocation potential and type of plant species with their stage of maturity^{18,19}. According to Van-Assche²⁰ the hyperaccumulation of metals in plant tissues induces oxidative stress by generating reactive oxygen species, which can cause disruption of normal physiological and biochemical functions of plants. It is therefore, necessary to know the physico-chemical properties of wastewater and particularly their elemental contents, before applied to the land. The present study focuses on the analysis of industrial wastewater, characterization of agricultural soil and to examine the heavy metal (Pb, Cd, Mn, Zn and Cu) content in some selected vegetables grown on agricultural land receiving untreated wastewater.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Samples of untreated wastewater, top-soil (0–10 cm depths) and vegetables were collected randomly in triplicate from the industrialized urban area. The study was carried out in Asansol industrial zone, Paschim Bardhaman District, West Bengal, India; consisting of a number of large and small scale industries, sponge iron and ferroalloy industries with integrated captive power plants. A control site was also selected in nearby areas where groundwater was used for irrigation. The wastewater samples were collected at regular intervals from open effluent channel in acid washed plastic containers (1L). Root zone surface soil samples (0–10 cm; n=8) were collected both from the wastewater irrigated and control site with the help of stainless steel spatula, and kept in zipped plastic bag. The sampling, preservation, and analysis of wastewater samples were carried out as per standard methods APHA²¹. Chloride (Cl⁻) concentration of wastewater samples was measured by AgNO₃ titration method; phosphate (PO₄³⁻) and nitrate (NO₃⁻) analysis was carried out using spectrophotometer. Sulfate concentration was measured by BaCl₂ method using spectrophotometer. Soil pH was

measured by preparing soil suspension (1 : 5, w/v) with deionised water²². Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined by extracting major cations from soil samples (5 g) with 1 M CH₃COONH₄ buffer followed by titrimetric analysis²³. Organic matter (OM) content was determined by Walkey and Black²⁴ method. To determine the total metal content (Pb, Cd, Mn, Zn and Cu), 1 g of soil sample was digested in microwave-oven with a mixture (4 : 1) of concentrated HNO₃ and HClO₄²⁵.

Samples of some commonly grown vegetables i.e. Pea (*Pisum sativum* L.), Family : Fabaceae; Beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*), Family : Fabaceae; Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.), Family : Chenopodiaceae; Brinjal (*Solanum melongena*), Family : Solanaceae; Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* L.), Family : Solanaceae; Radish (*Raphanus sativus* L.), Family : Brassicaceae – were collected both from the wastewater irrigated and control site. For metal analysis the edible parts (pea-fruit, beans-fruit, spinach-leaf, brinjal-fruit, tomato-fruit, radish-root) of the vegetable samples were used. Healthy and uninfected vegetable samples were collected at their stage of maturity; and care was also taken during sampling. In laboratory, sampled species were wash thoroughly first in tap water followed by distilled water, then become dried and analyzed for the determination of heavy metals. Heavy metal concentrations (Pb, Cd, Mn, Zn and Cu) of wastewater, soil, and vegetable samples were estimated by atomic absorption spectrometer (GBC, Avanta). The degree to which bioconcentration occurs is expressed as Bioconcentration factor (BCF) and can be calculated as follows: (BCF) = Metal concentration in vegetable samples (mg/kg of vegetable)/Metal concentration in soil (mg/kg of soil). BCF values < 1 indicating the low mobilities of metal to plants and > 1 indicating the high mobilities of metal to plants.

Results and discussion

Physico-chemical characteristics of irrigation water :

The physico-chemical properties of irrigation water along with different heavy metal concentrations are presented in Table 1. Any alteration in water pH is

Table 1. Physico-chemical analysis of untreated wastewater used for irrigation

Parameters	Range	Ave.	SD	IS standard ^a
pH	6.859–7.648	7.193	0.282	5.5–9.0
EC	380–560	466.667	62.823	–
TDS	243.63–352.18	298.744	37.867	–
TH	356–416	385.333	22.722	600
DO	2.838–4.075	3.460	0.529	–
COD	46.127–67.425	57.492	7.443	250
SO ₄ ²⁻	78.26–118.793	91.538	14.071	2.0
PO ₄ ³⁻	0.119–0.365	0.209	0.085	5.0
NO ₃ ⁻	0.224–0.516	0.351	0.106	100
Cl ⁻	36.465–57.742	47.697	7.527	–
Pb	0.082–0.279	0.168	0.072	0.10
Cd	0.007–0.098	0.029	0.034	2.0
Mn	0.697–0.875	0.808	0.069	–
Zn	0.595–0.887	0.711	0.098	5.0
Cu	0.362–0.482	0.421	0.053	3.0

All values are in mg/L except pH, EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$);

^aIS standard for inland surface water : IS 2490 Part I (1981).

accompanied by the change in other physico-chemical parameters; its values ranged from 6.859–7.648 with an average value 7.193 ± 0.282 . The electrical conductivity is a valuable indicator of the amount of material dissolved in water; and its values ranged from 380–560 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ with an average value 466.667 ± 62.823 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Total dissolved solids (TDS) indicates the general nature of water quality or salinity; and its values ranged from 243.63–352.18 mg/L with an average value 298.744 ± 37.867 mg/L. The measurement of the DO is an important parameter in water pollution studies as it indicates aerobic or anaerobic nature. The DO concentration ranged between 2.838–4.075 mg/L with an average value 3.460 ± 0.529 mg/L. The chemical oxygen demand (COD) of the wastewater ranged between 46.127–67.425 mg/L (Ave. : 57.492 ± 7.443 mg/L) which was much lower than the limit of 250 mg/L prescribed by the IS standard (1981)²⁶. The average value of PO₄³⁻ was 0.209 ± 0.085 mg/L and average NO₃⁻ was 0.351 ± 0.106 mg/L and these values were lower than the prescribed standards by IS standard²⁶; whereas SO₄²⁻ (Ave. : 91.538 ± 14.071 mg/L) exceeding the IS standard²⁶. The Cl⁻ concentration can

be used as an indicator for water pollution and the value ranged from 36.465–57.742 mg/L (Ave. : 47.697 ± 7.527 mg/L). The investigation reflected that the concentrations of various nutrients were very low in the wastewater, while SO₄²⁻ contents were in very high range. The concentrations (mg/L) of heavy metals in the wastewater samples ranged between Pb : 0.082–0.279, Cd : 0.007–0.098, Mn : 0.697–0.875, Zn : 0.595–0.887 and Cu : 0.362–0.482, whereas at control site, heavy metal concentrations in irrigation water were very low or below the detectable limits. The average Pb concentrations in the irrigated wastewater were exceeded the IS standard²⁶.

pH, OM, CEC and metal concentration in soil :

Metal content along with pH, OM and CEC in the contaminated and control soil is represented in Table 2. The wastewater irrigated soil exhibited acidic pH in the range of 6.284–6.712 with an overall mean of 6.547 ± 0.154 , whereas the control soil exhibited acidic to the alkaline type of soil in the range of 6.621–7.368 with an overall mean of 7.096 ± 0.306 . The organic matter content ranged from 1.986–2.852% with an overall mean of 2.564 ± 0.301 % in wastewater irrigated soil, and 1.846–2.218% with

Table 2. Distribution of heavy metals (mg/kg) in wastewater irrigated and control soils

Parameters	Wastewater irrigated soil				Control soil			
	Min.	Max.	Ave.	SD	Min.	Max.	Ave.	SD
pH	6.284	6.712	6.547	0.154	6.621	7.368	7.096	0.306
CEC	12.816	17.385	15.599	1.677	10.356	12.216	11.171	0.856
OM	1.986	2.852	2.564	0.301	1.846	2.218	1.997	0.152
Pb	68.964	85.231	76.551	5.302	29.537	38.192	34.944	3.107
Cd	2.289	3.521	2.863	0.518	0.398	0.917	0.684	0.208
Mn	161.63	177.24	167.141	5.954	49.859	63.647	57.198	5.462
Zn	119.38	143.55	128.772	8.735	56.326	71.853	63.896	5.971
Cu	93.169	104.14	98.969	4.471	39.186	49.624	44.530	3.649

Unit : CEC : meq Na/100 g soil, OM : %, Metal : mg/kg.

an overall mean of $1.997 \pm 0.152\%$ in control soil. The average CEC (meq Na/100 g soil) of wastewater irrigated soil (15.599 ± 1.677) was higher than the control soil (11.171 ± 0.856). Several physico-chemical characteristics of the soil are known to affect the bioavailability and plant uptake of metals which include pH, OM content and CEC²⁷. pH values of the wastewater irrigated soil were low which also may favours the metal mobility.

Pb concentration ranged from 68.964–85.231 mg/kg with an average value 76.551 ± 5.302 mg/kg in the wastewater irrigated soil and 29.537–38.192 mg/kg with an average value 34.944 ± 3.107 mg/kg in the control soil. All the samples of the wastewater irrigated soil were exceeded the Pb standards (50 mg/kg) for uncontaminated soil²⁸. Cd concentration in the analysed samples ranged from 2.289–3.521 mg/kg (Ave. : 2.863 ± 0.518 mg/kg) at the wastewater irrigated site and 0.398–0.917 mg/kg (Ave. : 0.684 ± 0.208 mg/kg) at the control site. Cd concentrations in the wastewater irrigated soil were also exceeded the metal standards (1.0 mg/kg) for uncontaminated soil²⁸. The concentration (mg/kg) of Mn and Zn ranged from 161.63–177.24 and 119.38–143.55 with a mean of 167.141 ± 5.954 and 128.77 ± 8.735 respectively in the wastewater irrigated soil. Comparatively lower values of Mn (57.198 ± 5.462 mg/kg) and Zn (63.896 ± 5.971 mg/kg) were observed in the control site than the wastewater irrigated site. Zn concentrations (100 mg/kg) were within metal standards for uncontaminated soil²⁸.

Cu concentration in the analysed samples ranged from 93.169–104.14 mg/kg (Ave. : 98.97 ± 4.471 mg/kg) at the wastewater irrigated site and 39.186–49.624 mg/kg (Ave. : 44.530 ± 3.649 mg/kg) at the control site. Cu concentrations (30 mg/kg) were also exceeded both in the wastewater irrigated and control site²⁸. The total metal content in the wastewater irrigated soil was much higher in comparison to the control samples. From the results it was found that the metals accumulated in the wastewater irrigated soil were in the order of Mn > Zn > Cu > Pb > Cd. This high concentration of heavy metals indicates higher availability and distribution of metals in soil irrigation with contaminated wastewater and thereby increasing the average heavy metal concentration in cultivated vegetables. The levels of heavy metals in the wastewater are quite low, though the wastewater irrigated soil showed much higher concentrations of heavy metals.

Metals concentrations in edible parts of crop plants :

Accumulation of metals in different edible parts of crop plants is represented in Table 3. The application of untreated wastewater generally leads to changes in the physico-chemical characteristics of soil and consequently heavy metal uptake by crops/vegetables. The study revealed that heavy metal concentrations showed variations among different vegetables/crops collected from control and wastewater irrigated sites. According to Sharma *et al.*²⁹ metal absorption and their accumulation in plant tissues depend upon vari-

Table 3. Heavy metal accumulation in wastewater irrigated crop plants

Plants	Soil	Pb		Cd		Mn		Zn		Cu	
		Conc.	BCF	Conc.	BCF	Conc.	BCF	Conc.	BCF	Conc.	BCF
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	WW	11.485	0.150	9.742	3.403	37.532	0.225	33.216	0.258	21.812	0.220
(Fruit)	Cont	6.271	0.179	0.847	1.238	52.148	0.912	39.572	0.619	28.751	0.646
<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	WW	14.195	0.185	9.865	3.446	51.415	0.308	43.117	0.335	19.461	0.197
(Fruit)	Cont	6.142	0.176	0.728	1.064	30.256	0.529	49.256	0.771	9.382	0.211
<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>	WW	31.152	0.407	9.241	3.228	78.354	0.469	52.469	0.407	33.653	0.340
(Leaf)	Cont	8.214	0.235	1.585	2.317	60.448	1.057	41.253	0.646	7.114	0.160
<i>Solanum melongena</i>	WW	33.197	0.434	5.264	1.839	81.457	0.487	47.318	0.367	32.929	0.333
(Fruit)	Cont	5.169	0.148	0.693	1.013	32.488	0.568	34.167	0.535	7.723	0.173
<i>Lycopersicum esculatum</i>	WW	2.715	0.035	1.956	0.683	23.254	0.139	38.185	0.297	10.446	0.106
(Fruit)	Cont	0.518	0.015	0.529	0.773	18.114	0.317	51.524	0.806	3.412	0.077
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	WW	24.627	0.322	4.735	1.654	104.19	0.623	41.185	0.320	19.734	0.199
(Root)	Cont	4.336	0.124	0.868	1.269	57.425	1.004	35.262	0.552	5.742	0.129

Unit : Heavy metal concentration : mg kg⁻¹ DM; DM – dry matter; WW – wastewater irrigated soil; Cont – control soil; BCF : Bioconcentration factor.

ous factors, which include temperature, moisture, pH, and nutrient availability. High level of Pb concentration (Ave. : 33.197 mg/kg; BCF : 0.434) was found in *Solanum melongena* and *Spinacia oleracea* (Ave. : 31.152 mg/kg; BCF : 0.407) followed by *Raphanus sativus* (Ave. : 24.627 mg/kg; BCF : 0.322). Cd concentration in *Phaseolus vulgaris* (9.865 mg/kg) with its BCF value 3.446 was found to be highest in wastewater irrigated area. *Pisum sativum* (Ave. : 9.742 mg/kg; BCF : 3.403) and *Spinacia oleracea* (Ave. : 9.241 mg/kg; BCF : 3.228) were also showed similar higher Cd concentrations. In wastewater irrigated area the Mn concentration was highest in the *Raphanus sativus* (104.19 mg/kg) with BCF 0.623. Though BCF > 1 was observed in the *Spinacia oleracea* (1.057) and *Raphanus sativus* (1.004) at the control site. Zn concentration in *Spinacia oleracea* (52.469 mg/kg) with its BCF value 0.407 was found to be highest in wastewater irrigated area. High level of Zn concentration along with their BCF was observed in some vegetables at the control site also. *Spinacia oleracea* (Ave. : 33.653 mg/kg; BCF : 0.34) and *Solanum melongena* (Ave. : 32.929 mg/kg; BCF : 0.333) showed similar higher Cu concentration. The variations in heavy metal concentrations in vegetables of the different sites may be ascribed to their degree of metal pollution sources.

Metal concentrations in vegetables of the same site varied significantly may be due to the differences in their morphology and physiology for heavy metal uptake, exclusion, accumulation and retention³⁰. High level of metal concentrations was also observed in the other vegetables analyzed. This may be due to the accumulation of heavy metals in the agricultural soil due to long-term irrigation.

Conclusions

The results indicated a substantial build-up of heavy metals in soils and vegetables irrigated with industrial wastewater. Low pH values of the wastewater irrigated soil may favours the metal mobility. The present investigation reflected that the concentrations of various nutrients were very low in the wastewater, while Pb and SO₄²⁻ contents were in very high range. Metal concentrations were in higher magnitude at wastewater irrigated site than the unaffected control site. Average metal concentration in untreated wastewater was in the sequence of Mn > Zn > Cu > Pb > Cd, wastewater irrigated contaminated soil also followed the same sequence though BCF of the studied metals followed the sequence of Cd > Mn > Zn > Pb > Cu. This study also reflected that the vegetables grown in contaminated soil showed significant accumulation of heavy met-

als in plant tissue. Among the studied metals, Cd is of greater concern due to its higher rates of plant uptake and accumulation in edible parts. However, the regular monitoring of heavy metals in irrigation water, agricultural soil and in vegetables grown on contaminated area is essential to prevent excessive build-up of these metals in the food chain.

References

1. C. Bilos, J. C. Colombo, C. N. Skorupka and P. M. J. Rodriguez, *Environ. Pollut.*, 2001, **11**, 149.
2. Y. J. Cui, Y. G. Zhu, R. Zhai, Y. Huang, Y. Qiu and J. Liang, *Environ. Int.*, 2005, **31**, 784.
3. N. Gupta, D. K. Khan and S. C. Santra, *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 2008, **80**, 115.
4. L. E. Hellen and O. C. Othman, *Int. J. Environ. Monit. Anal.*, 2016, **4**, 82.
5. P. S. Rao, T. Thomas, A. Hasan and A. David, *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.*, 2017, **6**, 2909.
6. B. Hu, X. Jia, J. Hu, D. Xu, F. Xia and Y. Li, *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 2017, **14**, 1042.
7. M. Webb (Ed.), "The Chemistry, Biochemistry and Biology of Cadmium", Elsevier, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 1979.
8. J. O. Nriagu, "Cadmium in the Environment. I. Ecological Cycling", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1980.
9. A. Sharma, A. Mukherjee and G. Talukder, *Curr. Sci.*, 1985, **54**, 539.
10. G. Tyler, A. M. Pahlsson, G. Bengrsson, E. Baath and L. Tranvik, *Water, Air Soil Pollut.*, 1989, **47**, 189.
11. WHO (World Health Organization), "Environmental Health Criteria", Geneva, 1992, Vol. 134.
12. M. Bhattacharya and M. A. Chaudhuri, *Indian J. Env. Bull.*, 1995, **33**, 236.
13. L. Jarup, *British Medical Bulletin*, 2003, **68**, 167.
14. C. P. Jordao, C. C. Nascentes, P. R. Cecon, R. L. F. Fontes and J. L. Pereira, *Environ. Monit. Assess.*, 2006, **112**, 309.
15. X. Xian and G. Shokohifard, *Water Air Soil Pollut.*, 1989, **45**, 265.
16. M. L. Otte, M. S. Haarsma, R. A. Broekman and J. Rozema, *Environ. Pollut.*, 1993, **82**, 13.
17. S. S. Mandaokar, D. M. Dharmadhikari and S. S. Dara, *Environ. Pollut.*, 1994, **83**, 277.
18. S. C. Barman, R. K. Sahu, S. K. Bhargava and C. Chatterjee, *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 2000, **64**, 489.
19. S. Sinha, A. K. Gupta, K. Bhatt, K. Pandey, U. N. Rai and K. P. Singh, *Environ. Monit. Assess.*, 2006, **115**, 1.
20. F. Van-Assche and H. Clisjsters, *Plant, Cell and Environment*, 1990, **13**, 195.
21. Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water, APHA (American Public Health Association), 20th ed., Washington, DC, 1998.
22. J. D. Rhoades in "Soluble Salts", eds. A. L. Page, R. H. Miller and D. R. Keeney, American Society of Agronomy, 2nd ed., Madison, WI, USA, 1982.
23. L. P. Reeuwijk (Ed.), "Procedure for Soil Analysis Technical Paper", 5th ed., ISRIC, Wageningen, The Netherlands, 1995.
24. A. Walkey and I. A. Black, *Soil Sci.*, 1934, **37**, 29.
25. M. J. Buchaure, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1973, **7**, 131.
26. IS 2490 Part I, "General Limits", Bureau of Indian Standards, 1981.
27. D. C. Adriano, "Trace Elements in Terrestrial Environments", 2nd ed., Springer, New York, 2001.
28. A. Kabata-Pendias and H. Pendias, "Trace Elements in Soil and Plants", 2nd ed., CRC, Boca Raton, 1992, 365.
29. R. K. Sharma, M. Agrawal and F. Marshal, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.*, 2007, **66(2)**, 258.
30. A. Kumar, I. K. Sharma, A. Sharma, S. Varshney and P. S. Verma, *Electron. J. Environ. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2009, **8(2)**, 9.